

```

CNNDescLang : cndesclang = (Architecture);

Architecture : input = ('input') fe += (FeatureExtraction)+ (inter
= (Interstice) class += (Classification)+)? output = ('output');

Dropout : 'dropout';

Pooling : 'avg_pooling' — 'max_pooling';

Convolution : (bnconv = 'bnconv') — (convbn = 'convbn') —
(conv = 'conv');

GlobalPooling : ('global_avg_pooling') — ("global_max_pooling");

FlattenOrGlobal : (flat='flatten') — (gp = GlobalPooling);

Interstice : fg = (FlattenOrGlobal);

Classification : drop = (Dropout)? d=('dense');

ConvDrop : conv = Convolution (drop = Dropout)?;

MergeConv : merge=Merge convdrop += (ConvDrop)*;

ConvOrMerge : convdrop += (ConvDrop)+ — convdrop += (ConvDrop)*
mergeConv += MergeConv+;

Left : (p=Pooling)? com=ConvOrMerge (pool=Pooling)?;

Right : conv += Convolution+ — {Right} empty = 'Empty';

MergeBody : '(' left = Left virg=',' right = Right ')';

Merge : db = '[' (mergeBody+=MergeBody)+ fm = ']';

FeatureExtraction : (conv = Convolution — merge = (Merge))
drop = (Dropout)? pool = (Pooling)?;

```

Figure 1: CNNGen grammar rules